

Supplementary Material 2

Semi-structured evaluation questionnaire (participants)

The following statements are about to the Strolll intervention. With Strolll we mean the exercises you played with the augmented-reality glasses at home, as prescribed by the therapist. Please indicate to what extent you agree with each of the following statements.

Following questions are about the Strolll intervention at home

1. To be able to train with Strolll, I had to give up other daily activities.

- Totally disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Totally agree

If you had to give up any daily activities, please indicate what they were:

2. Training at home with Strolll is a good addition to my current (physio)therapy.

- Totally disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Totally agree

Could you please explain your answer?

3. I enjoyed training with Strolll whenever it fitted my schedule.

- Totally disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Totally agree

Could you please explain your answer?

4. I enjoyed training in my own home.

- Totally disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Totally agree

Could you please explain your answer?

5. I found the remote supervision of the therapist sufficient to train with Strolll.

- Totally disagree
- Disagree

- Neutral
- Agree
- Totally agree

Could you please explain your answer?

6. The fact that the therapist could see remotely if I did my exercises at home motivates me to train.

- Totally disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Totally agree

Could you please explain your answer?

7. I felt safe while training at home with Strolll.

- Totally disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Totally agree

Could you please explain your answer?

8. During the training with Strolll AR, I was afraid of falling.

- Totally disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Totally agree

Could you please explain your answer?

For the questions below, indicate to what extent your skills have changed over the past 8 weeks.

9. Over the past eight weeks, my walking ability has:

- Significantly worsened
- Slightly worsened
- Remained the same
- Slightly improved
- Significantly improved

Could you please explain your answer?

10. Over the past eight weeks, my balance has:

- Significantly worsened
- Slightly worsened
- Remained the same

- Slightly improved
- Significantly improved

Could you please explain your answer?

11. Over the past eight weeks, my arm function has:

- Significantly worsened
- Slightly worsened
- Remained the same
- Slightly improved
- Significantly improved

Could you please explain your answer?

12. Over the past eight weeks, my cognitive abilities (such as attention, concentration, and memory) has:

- Significantly worsened
- Slightly worsened
- Remained the same
- Slightly improved
- Significantly improved

Could you please explain your answer?

Please answer the following question on a scale of 0 to 10. Here, a 0 means 'very unlikely' and a 10 means 'very likely'.

13. How likely are you to recommend the Strolll intervention to a friend (post-stroke)?

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
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Very unlikely

Very likely

Technology acceptance

The questions below are about the Strolll intervention. Please indicate to what extent you agree with each of the following statements.

	Totally disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Totally agree
1. I now know how to use Strolll.					
2. It was easy to use Strolll independently.					
3. In case of technical problems with Strolll, I could get help from someone.					
4. It was easy to learn how Strolll works.					
5. I would like to use Strolll regularly if I could keep the glasses.					
6. My living environment is suitable for the use of Strolll.					
7. My therapist encouraged the use of Strolll throughout the study.					
8. Strolll helps me to improve my gait and balance.					
9. Strolll helps me to improve my arm function.					
10. Strolll helps me to be more physically active.					
11. I find Strolll useful to use at home to train gait and balance.					
12. I find Strolll useful to use at home to train arm function.					
13. I would continue to train with Strolll if I could keep the glasses.					
14. It was clear and understandable how Strolll works.					
15. People who are important to me encouraged me to use Strolll.					
16. It was easy to get comfortable using Strolll.					
17. Using Strolll can improve my physical health.					
18. I would like to continue using Strolll in the future.					
19. People who influence my behavior encouraged me to use Strolll.					

Top-3 barriers and facilitators of Strolll

This top-3 barriers and facilitators is about the Strolll intervention performed at home prescribed and individualized by the therapist. Fill out the top 3 based on what you know about Strolll and based on what you have experienced during the study. There are no right or wrong answers. Try to answer as honestly as possible.

What do you think are the **main advantages** of Strolll for you as a person post-stroke if you could use Strolll in the future? Give a **top 3** and rank the advantages in order of importance, with the most important advantage at 1. Give a brief explanation of each advantage.

1. _____
Explanation: _____

2. _____
Explanation: _____

3. _____
Explanation: _____

What do you think are the **main disadvantages** of Strolll for you as a person post-stroke if you could use Strolll in the future? Give a **top 3** and rank the disadvantages in order of importance, with the most important disadvantage at 1. Give a brief explanation of each disadvantage.

1. _____
Explanation: _____

2. _____
Explanation: _____

3. _____
Explanation: _____

Semi-structured evaluation questionnaire (therapists)

We would like to know whether you changed usual care of the participants during the Stroll intervention period compared to before the intervention.

1. I had to adjust participants' usual care because of the addition of training with Stroll.

Yes

No

2. If the answer to the previous question was 'Yes': what adjustments did you make to the participants' usual care (frequency, type of exercises, type of sessions [group setting, individual, home exercises])?

Technology acceptance questionnaire

The questions below are about the Strolll intervention. Please indicate to what extent you agree with each of the following statements.

	Totally disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Totally agree	NA
1. I now know how to use Strolll.						
2. It was easy to independently use Strolll.						
3. In case of technical problems with Strolll, I could get help from someone.						
4. It was easy to learn how Strolll works.						
5. I would like to use Strolll regularly if I could keep the glasses.						
6. My work environment is suitable for the use of Strolll.						
7. My supervisor encouraged the use of Strolll throughout the study.						
8. The Strolll training helps my patients to improve their gait and balance.						
9. The Strolll training helps my patients to improve their arm function.						
10. The Strolll training helps my patients to be more physically active.						
11. I find Strolll useful to use at home to train gait and balance.						
12. I find Strolll useful to use at home to train arm function.						
13. I would continue to train with Strolll if I could keep the glasses.						
14. It was clear and understandable how Strolll works.						
15. People who are important to me encouraged me to use Strolll.						
16. It was easy to get comfortable using Strolll.						
17. Using Strolll can help my patients to improve their physical health.						
18. I would like to continue using Strolll in the future.						
19. People who influence my behavior encouraged me to use Strolll.						

Top-3 barriers and facilitators of Strolll

This top 3 questionnaire is about Strolll, an augmented-reality exercise program for people post-stroke, which you have given to your patients in the past period. By Strolll we mean the exercise program as a whole, namely the augmented-reality home training with the various exercises and the web portal that you have used to prescribe the exercises.

Fill out the top 3 based on what you know about Strolll and based on what you have experienced during the study. There are no right or wrong answers. Try to answer as honestly as possible.

What do you think are the **main advantages of Strolll for you as a healthcare provider and/or for people post-stroke** if the intervention would be implemented in clinical practice? Make a **top 3** and indicate for each advantage whether it is an advantage for you as a healthcare provider or an advantage for someone post-stroke. Put the advantage in order of importance, with the most important benefit at number 1. So you may mention benefits for you (as a healthcare provider) as well as for people who had a stroke, but you don't have to. The point is that you name the (in your opinion) most important advantages. Give a brief explanation for each advantage.

1. _____
Explanation: _____

2. _____
Explanation: _____

3. _____
Explanation: _____

What are the **main disadvantages of Strolll for you as a healthcare provider and/or for people post-stroke** if the intervention would be implemented in clinical practice? Make a **top 3** and clearly indicate for each disadvantage whether it is a disadvantage for you as a healthcare provider or a disadvantage for someone post-stroke. Put the disadvantages in order of importance, with the most important disadvantage at 1. You may therefore mention disadvantages for you (as a healthcare provider) as well as for people post-stroke, but you do not have to. The point is that you name the (in your opinion) most important disadvantages. Give a brief explanation for each disadvantage.

1. _____
Explanation: _____

2. _____
Explanation: _____

3. _____
Explanation: _____
